

ISic4406

Imperial honorific for a member of the Severan dynasty

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

stone

Object

tabula

Editor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance

Excavated between 1999 and 2010 in re-use on the decumanus maximus, Capo Boeo

Coordinates

37.802778, 12.429402

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Marsala, Museo archeologico regionale Lilibeo Marsala - Baglio Anselmi

Physical Description

Fragment of a slab of stone (material not stated), reused in antiquity in the repair of the paving of the so-called 'decumanus maximus' of ancient Lilybaeum; broken on all sides.

Dimensions

Height 27 cm

Width 27 cm

Depth not recorded cm

Layout

Remains of five lines of Latin letters

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Tall narrow letters, implying a C2-3 AD date

Letter heights:

Lines 1-5: 60-70 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation: not recorded mm

Text

1. [Imp(eratori)Caes(ari)M(arco)Aur(elio)]
2. [AntoninoPioFel(ici)Aug(usto)]
3. [Parth(ico)Max(imo)Brit(annico)Max(imo)]
4. [G]erm(anico) M[ax] [(imo)pont(ifici)]
5. [ma]x(imo), trib(unicia) potest(ate)[---]
6. [imp(eratori)] IIII, co(n)s(uli) IIII[Ip(atr)ip(atr)iae]
7. res [p(ublica)]
8. [L]i,ly[bit] [(anorum)]

Apparatus

Text of Silvestrini 2020: 296

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

Silvestrini, Marina 2020. Un autorevole tribuno militare e una titolatura imperiale in due epigrafi inedite di Lilibeo. *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik*. 213: 294-300. At 298-299 no.2 with fig.6

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